

Digital Technologies in Education

Mirzayunusova Z.I.

senior lecturer at the Kokand
state pedagogical institute
zmirzayunusova@mail.ru

Azamjonov A.A.

master's candidate of the Yelabuga
institute of Kazan Federal University
azamatjonazamjonov@mail.ru

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Abstract: In connection with the development of information technology, changing requirements of the modern labor market, the issue of the use of digital technologies in the educational space is currently being updated. Modern employers need specialists who are fluent in the use of electronic technology in professional activities. Digital technologies are an integral part of society, provide ample opportunity for the formation of specialist competence. The article discusses the main digital educational technologies, among which stand out such as: cloud technology, mobile space, web quest, online courses and gamification. The functions of technologies are revealed: managerial, educational and communicative. The purpose of the article is to disclose the essence of digital technologies in the educational space and determine their advantages, which include visibility, accessibility, orientation on the individual abilities of students. Various digital technologies in the educational space are aimed at the comprehensive development of students, the development of their practical skills, increasing motivation for learning, as well as the simplification and convenience of teachers. It is shown that digital educational technologies in the educational space are a prerequisite for increasing the efficiency and effectiveness of the educational process.

Keywords: digital technologies, innovative technologies, motivation, mobile space, web quest, online course, gamification, educational space, Internet resources, online training, educational work, student, teacher.

Introduction

Statement of the problem in a general sense and its connection with important scientific and practical problems.

The development of digital technologies in education is a leading goal of Professional Education, which makes it possible to develop competitive qualities of students on the way to becoming a highly qualified specialist. In this regard, the central task of the teacher is the use of digital technologies in the educational process, taking into account the individual capabilities of the student [1].

The modern labor market has created the need for the training of highly qualified personnel, and therefore the use of innovative technologies in the field of education is being updated.

Currently, graduates with the ability to work with digital technologies are needed. One of the priorities of the educational institution is the formation of the skills of students not only to receive theoretical knowledge, but also to use information technology, independent acquisition and analysis of information.

In addition to high-tech textbooks and teaching aids, the use of digital technologies is also necessary in universities.

Digital education technologies are an innovative way to organize an educational process based on the use of electronic systems that provide visibility. The purpose of using digital technologies is to improve the quality and efficiency of the educational process, as well as to successfully socialize students [2].

An analysis of recent studies and publications that studied the sides of this problem and on which the author based his answer; to identify previously unsolved parts of the general problem. The issue of digital technology has been widely covered in scientific articles and research over the past few years. In the field of education, the issue of digital technologies was dealt with by such scientists and teachers as M.I. Makseenko , L.V. Shmelkova , E.L. Vartanova , S.S. Smirnov, A. Marey, L.V Orlova, A.Yu. Uvarov and others. As noted by A.Yu.Uvarov, the use of digital technologies should be carried out in conjunction with a "synergistic" update of educational content. Such an approach radically increases the quality of education.

According to L.V.Shmelkova, one of the priority qualities of a person corresponding to a digital space is the ability of an individual to master digital technologies and use them in professional activities. S.S. Smirnov, E.L. Vartakov and M.I. Makseenko considers digitalization as a managerial, cultural, behavioral, as well as infrastructural component of the educational process [2].

Among the reasons for the development of digital technologies in the educational system, many researchers note a decrease in the load on the classroom and an increase in the share of independent work. Therefore, in order to preserve and improve the quality of education, digital educational technologies are actively being introduced, which ensure the interaction of the teacher and the student .

Timely elimination of shortcomings in students ' knowledge acquisition.

Among the possibilities of digital technologies in the training of students, the following are noted:

- completing tasks and increasing the mobility of educational materials;
- increase student motivation;
- individualization of the educational process;
- increase the appearance of materials;
- express feedback to the teacher;

ensuring access to results immediately after completing the task .

Digital technologies are an integral part of the life of society, therefore, scientists argue, they are easily integrated into the educational process, since students are used to using various electronic tools in their lives, and this makes it easier for them to work with different technologies, easier to perceive electronic tools and information, and the possibility of mastering materials.

Digital technologies make it possible to distinguish the educational process, build it in accordance with the needs of each student, give assignments corresponding to the level of training, and thus improve the quality of training. The use of digital tools helps to create

conditions for the student to become an active subject of the educational process. From passive perception, it switches to active actions and participates in the performance of tasks.

METHODOLOGY

Formation of the goals of the article. The purpose of the article is to reveal the possibilities of digital educational technologies in the training of highly qualified specialists [3].

Task description. To achieve this goal, it is necessary to solve the following tasks:

- determination of the role of digital educational technologies in the field of Education;
- consideration of the main types of digital educational technologies and their application to the educational process.

RESULTS

Presentation of the main research material with the full justification of the obtained scientific results.

Of the main types of digital technology, the following can be distinguished: mobile education, cloud technology, online courses, games and web quests [4]. Now mobile education technology is the most in demand in the field of Education. Thanks to its application, the most convenient and effective cooperation and knowledge exchange will be possible. Subjects of the educational process can exchange material remotely using wireless networks, infrared functions of their personal computer, transfer mobile devices to a group of students.

Cloud technologies have convenient access to the network, allowing you to store a large amount of data and use it with minimal management efforts, that is, the cloud allows you to distribute, process and store data.

Thus, thanks to this technology, teachers and students can carry out group, collective activities remotely [5]. For example, create research projects, reports, presentations in the Home Group, independent work here, each student is responsible for their own section of study work, but at the same time can edit and modify other blocks. Changes made by each student are synchronized in a common document. Cloud technology can be applied on the basis of Distance Education [6]. For example, a teacher in the University's electronic system can place assignments, practical work and other written assignments, in which the student's task is reduced to the performance of exercises in the document created by the teacher. This can be the following types of tasks: filling in gaps in a table or text, answering questions, or continuing an idea. As the work progresses, the teacher checks the assignments because he has access to the document.

The next digital education technology is online courses offered to students for distance learning. A distinctive feature and advantage of this technology is its personality orientation. Training is carried out at any time convenient for the student, which allows you to get a qualified education in different directions in the most convenient form for the student.

Online education can be done in two forms, synchronous and asynchronous education. Synchronous education involves teaching the teacher and student at a certain time, while asynchronous education means teaching the student at any time convenient for him, i.e. the teacher develops the course and places it on an Internet platform, while students familiarize themselves with the material provided and complete assignments. The advantage of this technology is that students can understand and memorize as much time as they devote to learning the material being studied, depending on their individual capabilities, as well as return to the material that has passed at any time to revise the subject.

For didactic purposes, digital technology is used "gamification", the peculiarity of which is

that the educational material is not broadcast by the teacher in traditional lectures, but is obtained independently by students.

It allows the use of digital technologies and internet resources and integration into the scientific process of the educational institution, as well as the formation of professional competencies as a result of their use. Gamification allows the organization of scientific and research activities of students through a combination of gaming and social media technologies. Gamification allows students to increase motivation, activate academic and cognitive activity by applying a competitive and visualized approach aimed at solving practical problems of any level of complexity. The use of this digital technology contributes to the development of search activity, internal stimulants, such as moral principles, beliefs, self-esteem, etc.

The use of web quest technology is based on a set of problematic tasks with the organization of a role-playing game through the use of Internet resources. Webquest is an innovative technology for the organization of the educational process, covering various problems of the academic discipline, which involves an ambiguous solution to the problem.

This technology sets the task of developing student independence, creative abilities, and critical thinking, as well as increasing student enthusiasm and educational achievement.

Thus, this technology is an inclusive-based education, in which each subject of the educational process has the opportunity to use personal technical means, for example, a tablet, computer, laptop, smartphone, etc.

All digital technologies in the field of Education perform a number of functions, the main of which are education, management and communication.

Education includes the organization of e-learning through the identification, development, analysis, broadcast, distance learning of students and teachers.

The management function involves recording progress, i.e. making ratings, tables, charts, as well as developing electronic materials and evaluation tools. Communicative function is characterized by network interaction between the subjects of the educational space, that is, conducting online courses, webinars, various video conferences, broadcasts, etc.

CONCLUSIONS

Conclusions of the study and prospects for further research in this area. The advantages of digital technologies in the field of Education lie in the individualization of the educational process, in a person-oriented direction.

Thus, education is moving to a new level, where it is a priority not only to fulfill the requirements of the program, but also to take into account the interests and individual abilities of students. The use of digital educational technologies expands the worldview of students, opens up new opportunities for obtaining knowledge in the most interesting and understandable form.

Advantages include minimizing paperwork, simplifying teaching and student learning. Students develop practical skills. The use of digital technologies makes it possible to take education to a qualitatively new level, characterized by the openness of knowledge.

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